

III. BUILDING INDUCTION MOTOR MODEL

National Instruments developed LabVIEW software for the first time in the year 1986 for the Apple Macintosh Company. It was conceptualized as a programming environment for hardware control. The introduction of an interface between the Personnel Computer and the instrument which is to be controlled by software was the main aim. The graphical user interface, which is used to simulate the controlled instrument on the computer, monitors itself with the help of LabVIEW software [5].

Nowadays LabVIEW software is also compatible with other operating system such as Windows and Linux, etc. The word LabVIEW is an acronym for Laboratory Virtual Instrument Engineering Workbench which is a graphical programming language based on graphical icons instead of number of programming codes for simulation purpose. LabVIEW software allows the user to build their own set of virtual instrument easily. These programs are known as Virtual Instruments, due to their operational replica of physical instruments, like temperature monitor, spectral scopes, pressure gauges, cathode ray oscilloscopes, and multi-meters [6].

The inputs are known as controls and the outputs are known as indicators are placed on the graphic user interface (GUI) called Front Panel (FP). They communicate with each block diagram through terminals of the icons. In LabVIEW the data flow of the program will be from left to right, but in C/C++ programming codes will be executed in order of top to bottom, errors in the LabVIEW will be easily identified during the execution of the program itself [7].

IV. SIMULATION AND ANALYSIS OF INDUCTION MACHINE

Machine's modelling developed in LabVIEW software is based on the mathematical expressions. Mathematical equations are first derived then converted into models using icons from the arithmetic board for further implementation in LabVIEW for graphical analysis [8]–[14].

Simulation of induction motor load test needs certain parameters that are described in Table I. To analyze the parameters are considered to be an important factors.

TABLE I
LOAD TEST PARAMETER

S.No	Parameter	Input Values
1	Phase voltage	V_{ph}
2	Number of poles	P
3	Frequency	F
4	Stator Resistance	R_1
5	Stator Reactance	X_1
6	Rotor Resistance	R_2
7	Rotor Reactance	X_2
8	Magnetizing Reactance	X_m

The above said parameters are used to model the induction motor. By changing the above input parameters corresponding values can be obtained in the form of graphical representation.

TABLE II
MOTOR INTERNAL PARAMETER

Symbols	Parameter	Input Values
R_1	Rotor Resistance	9
R_2	Rotor Reactance	0.500
S_1	Stator Resistance	1.110
S_2	Stator Reactance	0.500
X_m	Magnetizing Reactance	27

Motor internal parameters are taken from the best operating conditions of induction motor these values are made constant for the simulations of motor. For a particular operating load condition these values are made constant. Parameters can be changed before simulating for different load condition. They corresponding characteristics curve can be drawn.

TABLE III
MOTOR INPUT TERMINAL

Symbols	Parameter	Input Values
V_{ph}	Phase voltage	220
H_z	Frequency	50
P	Number of poles	4

Values are made constant throughout the simulation because small changes in these input values will deviate simulation result.

TABLE IV
MOTOR CORE LOSS

Symbols	Parameter	Input Values
L	Core losses	300

Core loss is made constantly throughout the simulation because they won't change for a motor throughout its lifetime. So it's made as constant in this simulation.

A. Simulation of Induction Motor

Fig. 2 Voltage waveform of induction motor

Fig. 3 Current Waveform of Induction Motor

Current consumed by the motor here is 0.8 amperes. They measured in the milliseconds. Maximum current absorbed by the motor is 0.8 amperes. There are ripples due to the harmonics present.

$$s = \frac{n_s - n_m}{n_s} \quad (1)$$

$$T = \frac{3}{2\pi n_s} * \frac{sE_2^2 R_2}{R_2^2 + (sX_2)^2} \quad (2)$$

There are two main characteristics explained or concerned in the field of machine design they are classified into electrical characteristics and the other one is mechanical characteristics. Normally torque vs. speed characteristics is also known as mechanical characteristics. Electrical characteristics are further classified into the torque vs. Current characteristics and speed vs. current characteristics.

Fig. 4 Torque vs speed characteristics of induction motor

Torque vs. speed characteristics are drawn but is a single quadrant operation where the motoring region is only shown. Plugging and generating regions are avoided to reduce the complexity is modeling of the induction motor.

S.No	Speed	Torque
1	200	115
2	400	128
3	600	143
4	800	161
5	1000	184
6	1200	209
7	1400	202
8	1600	175

Mechanical characteristics of induction motor are to be analysed in that torque vs speed characteristics plays a major role in analyses of induction motor. In this simulation the torque vs speed characteristics are analysed for the study of an induction motor which are modelled by the mathematical calculation.

Fig. 5 Torque vs current characteristics of induction motor

Torque and current increases in a straight line due to the fact torque is directly proportional to the current. The maximum torque is directly proportional to square of rotor induced emf at the standstill.

Fig. 6 Speed vs current of induction motor

Speed vs current characteristics shows that whenever there is an increased in speed there will be decreased current. In Fig. 6 there relation between the speed and current is shown in an opposite direction when the speed tends to decrease automatically current starts to increase this shown in the graph where the modeled induction motor graph drawn during decreasing the speed.

V. CONCLUSION

The analysis of this experimental result shows that induction motor model was built with the LabVIEW software. It can be used to model and simulate the working process of induction motor by which motor performance calculated, is set to compare with the real time operating consideration of the induction motor for the optimal operation of machines.

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